

Mathematical Analysis of Cuboctahedron

Harish Chandra Rajpoot

M.M.M. University of Technology, Gorakhpur-273010 (UP), India

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Introduction: A cuboctahedron is a solid that has 8 congruent equilateral triangular & 6 congruent square faces, each having equal edge length. It is made/generated either by cutting off all the vertices (corners) of a cube (having 8 vertices & 6 congruent square faces) or by cutting off all the vertices (corners) of a regular octahedron (having 6 vertices & 8 congruent equilateral triangular faces) to generate 8 equilateral triangular & 6 square faces of equal edge length such that all the vertices lie on a sphere [1]. For calculating all the parameters of a cuboctahedron, we would use the equations of a right pyramid & cube (regular hexahedron) [2,3]. When a cube is cut off from the vertex, a right pyramid, with base as an equilateral triangle & certain normal height, is obtained. Since a cube has 8 vertices hence we obtain 8 congruent cut-off right pyramids, each with an equilateral triangular base.

Cutting off a cube: For ease of calculations, let there be a cube with edge length PQ (unknown) & its centre at the point C. Now all its 8 vertices are cut off to obtain a cuboctahedron. Thus each of the congruent square faces with edge length PQ is changed into a new reduced square face with edge length a (known) (see figure 1) & we obtain 8 congruent cut off right pyramids with base as an equilateral triangle corresponding to 8 vertices of the parent solid. (See figure 1 which shows one square face & a right pyramid with equilateral triangular base & normal height h being cut off from the cube).

$$\begin{aligned} \text{No. of congruent equilateral triangular faces in the cuboctahedron} \\ = \text{no. of vertices in parent cube} = 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{No. of congruent square faces in the cuboctahedron} = \text{no. of square faces in parent cube} = 6$$

$$\text{No. of vertices in the cuboctahedron} = 3 \times 8 - 12 = 12$$

Calculation of edge length of parent cube:

Let a be the edge length of each face of a cuboctahedron to be generated by cutting off all the vertices of a parent cube with edge length PQ (unknown).

In right $\triangle APB$

$$(AP)^2 + (PB)^2 = (AB)^2$$

$$2(AP)^2 = a^2 \quad (\text{since, } AP = PB \text{ \& } AB = a)$$

$$\Rightarrow AP = \frac{a}{\sqrt{2}}$$

\therefore edge length of parent cube, $PQ = PA + AQ$

$$= 2AP = \frac{2a}{\sqrt{2}} = a\sqrt{2} \quad (\text{since, } AP = AQ)$$

$$\therefore \text{edge length of parent cube, } PQ = a\sqrt{2}$$

Figure 1: Each of 12 congruent square faces with edge length $a\sqrt{2}$ of a cube is changed into a new reduced square face with edge length a by cutting off all the vertices. A right pyramid with base as an equilateral triangle with side length a & normal height h is being cut off from a cube with edge length $a\sqrt{2}$

Above result shows that if we are to generate a cuboctahedron with edge length a then we have to cut off all 8 vertices of a cube of edge length $a\sqrt{2}$

Analysis of cuboctahedron by using equations of right pyramid & cube

Now consider any of 8 congruent cut off right pyramids having base as an equilateral triangle ABD with side length a , normal height h & right angle 90° between any two consecutive lateral edges (see figure 2 below)

Normal height (h) of cut off right pyramid: We know that the normal height of any **right pyramid with regular polygonal base**, having n no. of sides each of length a & an angle α between any two consecutive lateral edges, is given as

$$H = \frac{a}{2} \sqrt{\cot^2 \frac{\alpha}{2} - \cot^2 \frac{\pi}{n}}$$

Figure 2: Normal distance (H_T) of equilateral triangular faces is always greater than the normal distance (H_s) of square faces measured from the centre C of any cuboctahedron.

$$\therefore h = \frac{a}{2} \sqrt{\cot^2 \frac{90^\circ}{2} - \cot^2 \frac{\pi}{3}} = \frac{a}{2} \sqrt{1 - \frac{1}{3}} \quad (\text{for equilateral triangular base, } n = 3)$$

$$\Rightarrow h = \frac{a}{2} \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} = \frac{a}{\sqrt{6}}$$

$$\therefore \text{cut off normal height, } h = \frac{a}{\sqrt{6}} \dots \dots \dots (I)$$

Volume (V') of cut off right pyramid: We know that the volume of a right pyramid is given as

$$= \frac{1}{3} (\text{area of base (equilateral triangle)}) \times (\text{normal height})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \therefore V' &= \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{1}{4} na^2 \cot \frac{\pi}{n} \right) \times h = \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{1}{4} \times 3 \times a^2 \cot \frac{\pi}{3} \right) \times \frac{a}{\sqrt{6}} \\ &= \frac{a^3}{4} \times \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \times \frac{1}{\sqrt{6}} = \frac{a^3}{12\sqrt{2}} \end{aligned}$$

$$V' = \frac{a^3}{12\sqrt{2}} \dots \dots \dots (II)$$

Normal distance (H_T) of equilateral triangular faces from the centre of cuboctahedron: The normal distance (H_T) of each of the equilateral triangular faces from the centre C of cuboctahedron is given as

$$H_T = OC = CP - OP \quad (\text{from the figure 2 above})$$

$$\Rightarrow H_T = (\text{outer (circumscribed) radius of parent cube}) - h$$

$$\Rightarrow H_T = \frac{\sqrt{3}(a\sqrt{2})}{2} - \frac{a}{\sqrt{6}} \quad (\text{outer radius is given from HCR's Formula})$$

$$= \frac{3a - a}{\sqrt{6}} = \frac{2a}{\sqrt{6}} = a \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}}$$

$$\Rightarrow H_T = a \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} \approx 0.81649658a \dots \dots \dots (III)$$

It's clear that all 8 congruent equilateral triangular faces are at an equal normal distance H_T from the centre of any cuboctahedron.

Solid angle (ω_T) subtended by each of the equilateral triangular faces at the centre of cuboctahedron: we know that the solid angle (ω) subtended by any regular polygon with each side of length a at any point lying at a distance H on the vertical axis passing through the centre of plane is given by HCR's Theory of Polygon [1,2] as follows

$$\omega = 2\pi - 2n \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{2H \sin \frac{\pi}{n}}{\sqrt{4H^2 + a^2 \cot^2 \frac{\pi}{n}}} \right)$$

Hence, by substituting the corresponding values in the above expression, we get the solid angle subtended by each equilateral triangular face at the centre of cuboctahedron as follows

$$\omega_T = 2\pi - 2 \times 3 \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{2 \left(a \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} \right) \sin \frac{\pi}{3}}{\sqrt{4 \left(a \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} \right)^2 + a^2 \cot^2 \frac{\pi}{3}}} \right)$$

$$= 2\pi - 6 \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{2 \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} \times \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}}{\sqrt{\frac{8}{3} + \frac{1}{3}}} \right) = 2\pi - 6 \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{3}} \right) = 2\pi - 6 \sin^{-1} \left(\sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} \right)$$

$$\omega_T = 2\pi - 6 \sin^{-1} \left(\sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} \right) \approx 0.551285598 \text{ sr} \quad \dots \dots \dots (IV)$$

Normal distance (H_s) of square faces from the centre of cuboctahedron: The normal distance (H_s) of each of the square faces from the centre C of cuboctahedron is given as

$$H_s = O'C \quad (\text{from the figure 2 above})$$

$$\Rightarrow H_s = (\text{inner (inscribed) radius of parent cube})$$

$$\Rightarrow H_s = \frac{(a\sqrt{2})}{2} = \frac{a}{\sqrt{2}} \quad (\text{inner radius is given from HCR's Formula})$$

$$\Rightarrow H_s = \frac{a}{\sqrt{2}} \approx 0.707106781a \quad \dots \dots \dots (V)$$

It's clear that all 6 congruent square faces are at an equal normal distance H_s from the centre of any cuboctahedron.

It's also clear from eq(III) & (V) $H_T > H_s$ i.e. the normal distance (H_T) of equilateral triangular faces is greater than the normal distance (H_s) of square faces from the centre of cuboctahedron i.e. square faces are much closer to the centre as compared to the equilateral triangular faces in any cuboctahedron.

Solid angle (ω_s) subtended by each of the square faces at the centre of cuboctahedron: we know that the solid angle (ω) subtended by any regular polygon is given by **HCR's Theory of Polygon** [1,2] as follows

$$\omega = 2\pi - 2n \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{2H \sin \frac{\pi}{n}}{\sqrt{4H^2 + a^2 \cot^2 \frac{\pi}{n}}} \right)$$

Hence, by substituting the corresponding value of normal distance $H = H_s$ in the above expression, we get the solid angle subtended by each square face at the centre of cuboctahedron as follows

$$\omega_s = 2\pi - 2 \times 4 \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{2 \left(\frac{a}{\sqrt{2}} \right) \sin \frac{\pi}{4}}{\sqrt{4 \left(\frac{a}{\sqrt{2}} \right)^2 + a^2 \cot^2 \frac{\pi}{4}}} \right) \quad (\text{for square, } n = 4)$$

$$= 2\pi - 8 \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{\sqrt{2} \times \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}}{\sqrt{2+1}} \right) = 2\pi - 8 \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \right)$$

$$\omega_s = 2\pi - 8 \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \right) \approx 1.359347638 \text{ sr} \quad \dots \dots \dots (VI)$$

It's clear that the solid angle subtended by each of the square faces is greater than the solid angle subtended by each of the equilateral triangular faces at the centre of any cuboctahedron.

Important parameters of a cuboctahedron:

- 1. Inner (inscribed) radius(R_i):** It is the radius of the largest sphere inscribed (trapped inside) by cuboctahedron. The largest inscribed sphere always touches all 6 congruent square faces but does not touch any of 8 congruent equilateral triangular faces at all since all 6 square faces are closer to the centre as compared to all 8 triangular faces. Thus, inner radius is always equal to the normal distance (H_s) of square faces from the centre of a cuboctahedron & is given from the eq(V) as follows

$$R_i = H_s = \frac{a}{\sqrt{2}} \approx 0.707106781a$$

Hence, the **volume of inscribed sphere** is given as

$$V_{inscribed} = \frac{4}{3} \pi (R_i)^3 = \frac{4}{3} \pi \left(\frac{a}{\sqrt{2}} \right)^3 \approx 1.480960979a^3$$

- 2. Outer (circumscribed) radius(R_o):** It is the radius of the smallest sphere circumscribing a given cuboctahedron or it's the radius of a spherical surface passing through all 12 vertices of a given cuboctahedron. It is calculated as follows (See Figure 2 above).

$$R_o = \text{distance of any of the vertices from the centre } C = CA = CB = CD$$

In right ΔOMA

$$\sin \angle AOM = \frac{AM}{OA} \Rightarrow \sin 60^\circ = \frac{\left(\frac{a}{2}\right)}{OA} \quad \text{or } OA = \frac{a}{2 \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}\right)} = \frac{a}{\sqrt{3}} \quad \left(\text{since, } \angle AOB = \frac{2\pi}{3} = 120^\circ \right)$$

In right ΔAOC

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow CA = \sqrt{(OA)^2 + (OC)^2} &= \sqrt{\left(\frac{a}{\sqrt{3}}\right)^2 + \left(a \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}}\right)^2} && \text{(since, } OC = H_T) \\ &= a \sqrt{\frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3}} = a = \text{outer (circumscribed) radius} \end{aligned}$$

Hence, the outer radius of cuboctahedron is given as

$$R_o = a$$

Hence, the **volume of circumscribed sphere** is given as

$$V_{\text{circumscribed}} = \frac{4}{3}\pi(R_o)^3 = \frac{4}{3}\pi a^3$$

3. **Surface area (A_s):** We know that a cuboctahedron has 8 congruent equilateral triangular & 6 congruent square faces each of edge length a . Hence, its surface area is given as follows

$$A_s = 8 \times (\text{area of equilateral triangle}) + 6 \times (\text{area of square})$$

We know that **area of any regular n-polygon** with each side of length a is given as

$$A = \frac{1}{4}na^2 \cot \frac{\pi}{n}$$

Hence, by substituting all the corresponding values in the above expression, we get

$$A_s = 8 \times \left(\frac{1}{4} \times 3a^2 \cot \frac{\pi}{3}\right) + 6 \times \left(\frac{1}{4} \times 4a^2 \cot \frac{\pi}{4}\right) = 6a^2 \times \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} + 6a^2 = (6 + 2\sqrt{3})a^2$$

$$A_s = (6 + 2\sqrt{3})a^2 \approx 9.464101615a^2$$

4. **Volume (V):** We know that a cuboctahedron with edge length a is obtained by cutting a cube with edge length $a\sqrt{2}$ at all its 8 vertices. Thus, 8 congruent right pyramids with equilateral triangular base are cut off from the parent cube. Hence, the volume (V) of the cuboctahedron is given as follows

$$V = (\text{volume of parent cube}) - 8(\text{volume of cut off right pyramid})$$

$$= (a\sqrt{2})^3 - 8 \times (V') \quad (\text{volume of cube/hexahedron is given from HCR's formula})$$

$$= 2\sqrt{2}a^3 - 8 \times \frac{a^3}{12\sqrt{2}} \quad (\text{substituting the value of } V' \text{ from eq (II)})$$

$$= 2\sqrt{2}a^3 - \frac{\sqrt{2}a^3}{3} = \frac{(6\sqrt{2} - \sqrt{2})a^3}{3} = \frac{5\sqrt{2}a^3}{3}$$

$$V = \frac{5\sqrt{2}a^3}{3} \approx 2.357022604a^3$$

5. **Mean radius (R_m):** It is the radius of the sphere having a volume equal to that of a given cuboctahedron. It is calculated as follows

$$\text{volume of sphere with mean radius } R_m = \text{volume of given cuboctahedron}$$

$$\frac{4}{3}\pi(R_m)^3 = \frac{5\sqrt{2}a^3}{3} \Rightarrow (R_m)^3 = \frac{5a^3}{2\pi\sqrt{2}} \text{ or } R_m = a \left(\frac{5}{2\pi\sqrt{2}}\right)^{\frac{1}{3}}$$

$$R_m = a \left(\frac{5}{2\pi\sqrt{2}}\right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \approx 0.825578509a$$

It's clear from above results that $R_i < R_m < R_o$

Construction of a solid cuboctahedron: In order to construct a solid cuboctahedron with edge length a there are two methods

1. Construction from elementary right pyramids: In this method, first we construct all elementary right pyramids as follows

Construct 8 congruent right pyramids with equilateral triangular base of side length a & normal height (H_T)

$$H_T = a \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} \approx 0.81649658a$$

Construct 6 congruent right pyramids with square base of side length a & normal height (H_s)

$$H_s = \frac{a}{\sqrt{2}} \approx 0.707106781a$$

Now, paste/bond by joining all these elementary right pyramids by overlapping their lateral surfaces & keeping their apex points coincident with each other such that all the edges of each equilateral triangular base (face) coincide with the edges of three square bases (faces). Thus, a solid cuboctahedron, with 8 congruent equilateral triangular & 6 congruent square faces each of edge length a , is obtained.

2. Facing a solid sphere: It is a method of facing, first we select a **blank as a solid sphere** of certain material (i.e. metal, alloy, composite material etc.) & with suitable diameter in order to obtain the maximum desired edge length of cuboctahedron. Then, we perform facing operations on the solid sphere to generate 8 congruent equilateral triangular & 6 congruent square faces each of equal edge length.

Let there be a blank as a solid sphere with a diameter D . Then the edge length a , of a cuboctahedron of the maximum volume to be produced, can be co-related with the diameter D by **relation of outer radius (R_o) with edge length (a) of a cuboctahedron** as follows

$$R_o = a$$

Now, substituting $R_o = D/2$ in the above expression, we have

$$\frac{D}{2} = a \quad \text{or} \quad a = \frac{D}{2}$$

$$a = \frac{D}{2}$$

Above relation is very useful for determining the edge length a of a cuboctahedron to be produced from a solid sphere with known diameter D for manufacturing purpose.

Hence, the **maximum volume of cuboctahedron** produced from the solid sphere is given as follows

$$V_{max} = \frac{5\sqrt{2}a^3}{3} = \frac{5\sqrt{2}}{3} \left(\frac{D}{2}\right)^3 = \frac{5\sqrt{2}D^3}{24} = \frac{5D^3}{12\sqrt{2}}$$

$$V_{max} = \frac{5D^3}{12\sqrt{2}} \approx 0.294627825D^3$$

Minimum volume of material removed is given as

$$(V_{removed})_{min} = (\text{volume of parent sphere with diameter } D) - (\text{volume of cuboctahedron})$$

$$= \frac{\pi}{6}D^3 - \frac{5D^3}{12\sqrt{2}} = \left(\frac{\pi}{6} - \frac{5}{12\sqrt{2}}\right)D^3$$

$$(V_{removed})_{min} = \left(\frac{\pi}{6} - \frac{5}{12\sqrt{2}}\right) D^3 \approx 0.22897095D^3$$

Percentage (%) of minimum volume of material removed

$$\% \text{ of } V_{removed} = \frac{\text{minimum volume removed}}{\text{total volume of sphere}} \times 100$$

$$= \frac{\left(\frac{\pi}{6} - \frac{5}{12\sqrt{2}}\right) D^3}{\frac{\pi}{6} D^3} \times 100 = \left(1 - \frac{5}{2\pi\sqrt{2}}\right) \times 100 \approx 43.73\%$$

It's obvious that when a cuboctahedron of the maximum volume is produced from a solid sphere then about 43.73% of material is removed as scraps. Thus, we can select optimum diameter of blank as a solid sphere to produce a solid cuboctahedron of the maximum volume (or with maximum desired edge length)

Conclusions: let there be any cuboctahedron having 8 congruent equilateral triangular & 6 congruent square faces each with edge length a then all its important parameters are calculated/determined as tabulated below

Congruent polygonal faces	No. of faces	Normal distance of each face from the centre of the given cuboctahedron	Solid angle subtended by each face at the centre of the given cuboctahedron
Equilateral triangle	8	$a \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} \approx 0.81649658a$	$2\pi - 6 \sin^{-1}\left(\sqrt{\frac{2}{3}}\right)$ $\approx 0.551285598 \text{ sr}$
Square	6	$\frac{a}{\sqrt{2}} \approx 0.707106781a$	$2\pi - 8 \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}\right)$ $\approx 1.359347638 \text{ sr}$

Inner (inscribed) radius (R_i)	$R_i = \frac{a}{\sqrt{2}} \approx 0.707106781a$
Outer (circumscribed) radius (R_o)	$R_o = a$
Mean radius (R_m)	$R_m = a \left(\frac{5}{2\pi\sqrt{2}}\right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \approx 0.825578509a$
Surface area (A_s)	$A_s = (6 + 2\sqrt{3})a^2 \approx 9.464101615a^2$
Volume (V)	$V = \frac{5\sqrt{2}}{3}a^3 \approx 2.357022604a^3$

Note: Above articles had been developed & *illustrated* by Mr H.C. Rajpoot (B Tech, Mechanical Engineering)

M.M.M. University of Technology, Gorakhpur-273010 (UP) India

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Email: rajpootharishchandra@gmail.com

Author's Home Page: <https://notionpress.com/author/HarishChandraRajpoot>

Courtesy: *Advanced Geometry* by Harish Chandra Rajpoot

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